

In Markov process, an extremal reversible measure is an extremal invariant measure.

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Abstract:

We consider a discrete-time temporally-homogeneous conservative Markov process. We show that extremality of reversible measure implies extremality of invariant measure. Using analogue of Dirichlet form, we modify a proof that in stochastic Ising model (Glauber dynamics), an extreme Gibbs state is an extreme invariant measure.

Keyword:

Choquet simplex, ergodic decomposition, detailed balance condition, mutual singularity.

1 Introduction

Let (X, \mathcal{B}) be a measurable space. Let $\{P^x\}_{x \in X}$ be a discrete-time temporally-homogeneous Markov process whose state-space is (X, \mathcal{B}) . Let $\{p(x, E)\}_{x \in X, E \in \mathcal{B}}$ be the transition function of $\{P^x\}_{x \in X}$. That is,

$$p(x, E) := P^x(\eta(1) \in E).$$

$\{P^x\}_{x \in X}$ is conservative, if and only if for any $x \in X$, $p(x, X) = 1$ holds.

Definition 1 (extreme element): Let C be a subset of the set of all probability measures on (X, \mathcal{B}) . Let $m \in C$. Then, m is said to be an *extreme element* of C , if and only if $[t \in (0, 1), m_0, m_1 \in C, m = (1 - t)m_0 + tm_1]$ implies $m_0 = m_1$. \square

Definition 2 (T): Let define the linear map T from the set of all \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable functions to the set of all \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable functions by

$$(Tf)(x) := \int_{y \in X} f(y)p(x, dy).$$

\square

Definition 3 ($\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{G}, \mathcal{I}_e, \mathcal{R}_e, \mathcal{G}_e$): (1) Let m be a probability measure on (X, \mathcal{B}) . Then, m is said to be an *invariant measure*, if and only if for any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function f ,

$$\int_{x \in X} (Tf)(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} f(x)m(dx)$$

holds. m is said to be a *reversible measure*, if and only if for any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable functions f and g ,

$$\int_{x \in X} (Tf)(x)g(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} f(x)(Tg)(x)m(dx)$$

holds. m is said to be a *conservative measure*, if and only if for any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function g ,

$$\int_{x \in X} (T1)(x)g(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} g(x)m(dx)$$

holds.

(2) Let define \mathcal{I} as the set of *all invariant measures*. Let define \mathcal{I}_e as the set of all extreme elements of \mathcal{I} . Let define \mathcal{R} as the set of *all reversible measures*. Let define \mathcal{R}_e as the set of all extreme elements of \mathcal{R} . Let define \mathcal{G} as the set of *all conservative reversible measures*. Let define \mathcal{G}_e as the set of all extreme elements of \mathcal{G} . \square

Theorem 4 (Main Result): *Suppose that $\{P^x\}_{x \in X}$ is conservative. Then, $\mathcal{R}_e \subset \mathcal{I}_e$ holds.* \square

2 Proof

Definition 5 (joint distribution σ_m): For each probability measure m on (X, \mathcal{B}) , let define σ_m as the joint distribution with m as the initial distribution and $\{0, 1\}$ as the set of times. That is,

$$\sigma_m(C) := \int_{x_0 \in X} \left(\int_{x_1 \in X} 1_C(x_0, x_1) p(x_0, dx_1) \right) m(dx_0).$$

□

Lemma 6: *Let $m \in \mathcal{R}$. Then, σ_m is symmetric.*

Proof: Because of $\sigma_m(A \times B) = \int_{x_0 \in X} (\int_{x_1 \in X} 1_A(x_0) 1_B(x_1) p(x_0, dx_1)) m(dx_0) = \int_{x_0 \in X} 1_A(x_0) (T1_B)(x_0) m(dx_0) = \int_{x_0 \in X} 1_B(x_0) (T1_A)(x_0) m(dx_0) = \int_{x_0 \in X} (\int_{x_1 \in X} 1_B(x_0) 1_A(x_1) p(x_0, dx_1)) m(dx_0) = \sigma_m(B \times A)$, it is symmetric (by Hopf extension theorem). ■

The following lemma is the basis in this section. It was inspired by the formula (1.4.8) in [1].

Lemma 7 (quadratic form): *Let $m \in \mathcal{G}$. Then, for any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function f ,*

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{x \in X} ((1 - T)f)(x) f(x) m(dx) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{(x_0, x_1) \in X^2} |f(x_0) - f(x_1)|^2 \sigma_m(d(x_0, x_1)) \end{aligned}$$

holds.

Proof: From Lemma 6, $2 \int_{x \in X} ((1 - T)f)(x) f(x) m(dx) = 2 \int_{x \in X} f(x) (f(x)(T1)(x) - (Tf)(x)) m(dx) = 2 \int_{x_0 \in X} f(x_0) (\int_{x_1 \in X} (f(x_0) - f(x_1)) p(x_0, dx_1)) m(dx_0) = 2 \int_{(x_0, x_1) \in X^2} f(x_0) (f(x_0) - f(x_1)) \sigma_m(d(x_0, x_1)) = \int_{(x_0, x_1) \in X^2} f(x_0) (f(x_0) - f(x_1)) \sigma_m(d(x_0, x_1)) + \int_{(x_0, x_1) \in X^2} f(x_1) (f(x_1) - f(x_0)) \sigma_m(d(x_0, x_1)) = \int_{(x_0, x_1) \in X^2} |f(x_0) - f(x_1)|^2 \sigma_m(d(x_0, x_1))$ holds. ■

Lemma 8: *Let $m \in \mathcal{G}$. Let f be a \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function. Then, the followings (a), (b), (c) and (d) are equivalent.*

(a) *Let g be a \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function. Then,*

$$m\text{-a.s. } x : \quad (T(gf))(x) = (Tg)(x)f(x)$$

holds.

(b)

$$m\text{-a.s. } x : (Tf)(x) = f(x)$$

holds.

(c)

$$\int_{x \in X} ((1 - T)f)(x)f(x)m(dx) = 0$$

holds.

(d)

$$\sigma_m\text{-a.s. } (x_0, x_1) : f(x_0) = f(x_1)$$

holds.

Proof: (1) Suppose that (a) holds. We show (b). For any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function g , $\int_{x \in X} (Tf)(x)g(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} (T(1f))(x)g(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} (T1)(x)f(x)g(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} f(x)g(x)m(dx)$ holds.

(2) [(b) \Rightarrow (c)] is easy.

(3) From Lemma 7, [(c) \Rightarrow (d)] holds.

(4) Suppose that (d) holds. We show (a). Let g be a \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function. Then, for any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function h , $\int_{x \in X} h(x)(T(gf))(x)m(dx) = \int_{(x_0, x_1) \in X^2} h(x_0)g(x_1)f(x_1)\sigma_m(d(x_0, x_1)) = \int_{(x_0, x_1) \in X^2} h(x_0)g(x_1)f(x_0)\sigma_m(d(x_0, x_1)) = \int_{x \in X} h(x)(Tg)(x)f(x)m(dx)$ holds. ■

Lemma 9: Let $m \in \mathcal{G}$. Let ρ be a $[0, +\infty)$ -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function. Then, $\rho m \in \mathcal{G}$ holds, if and only if $\rho m \in \mathcal{I}$ holds.

Proof: (1) Suppose that $\rho m \in \mathcal{G}$ holds. We show that $\rho m \in \mathcal{I}$ holds. For any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function f , $\int_{x \in X} (Tf)(x)\rho(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} (T1)(x)f(x)\rho(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} f(x)\rho(x)m(dx)$ holds.

(2) Suppose that $\rho m \in \mathcal{I}$ holds. We show that $\rho m \in \mathcal{G}$ holds. For any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function f , $\int_{x \in X} f(x)(T\rho)(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} (Tf)(x)\rho(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} f(x)\rho(x)m(dx)$ holds. [m -a.s. $x : (T\rho)(x) = \rho(x)$] holds. From Lemma 8, for any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function g , [m -a.s. $x : (T(g\rho))(x) = (Tg)(x)\rho(x)$] holds. For any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable functions f and g , $\int_{x \in X} (Tf)(x)g(x)\rho(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} f(x)(T(g\rho))(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} f(x)(Tg)(x)\rho(x)m(dx)$ holds. ■

Lemma 10: $\mathcal{G}_e \subset \mathcal{I}_e$ holds.

Proof: Suppose that $m \in \mathcal{G}_e$ holds. We show that $m \in \mathcal{I}_e$ holds.

(1) For any \mathbb{R} -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function f , $\int_{x \in X} (Tf)(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} (T1)(x)f(x)m(dx) = \int_{x \in X} f(x)m(dx)$ holds.

(2) Suppose that $t \in (0, 1)$, $m_0, m_1 \in \mathcal{I}$ and $m = (1 - t)m_0 + tm_1$ hold. Then, $m_0 \leq \frac{1}{1-t}m$ and $m_1 \leq \frac{1}{t}m$ hold. There exist $[0, +\infty)$ -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable functions ρ_0 and ρ_1 such that $m_0 = \rho_0 m$ and $m_1 = \rho_1 m$ hold. From Lemma 9, $m_0, m_1 \in \mathcal{G}$ holds. $m_0 = m_1$ holds. ■

Proof of Main Result: $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{G}$ holds. So, from Lemma 10, $\mathcal{R}_e = \mathcal{G}_e \subset \mathcal{I}_e$ holds. ■

The following remark seems to be similar to the proposition (4.3.5) in [2]. Lemma 7 seems to be similar to the lemma (4.4.3) in [2]. As stochastic Ising model seems to be a typical example of symmetric Feller process, a reversible measure and a Gibbs measure are equivalent from the theorem (4.2.14) in [2]. While the corollary (4.4.20) in [2] asserts that an extreme Gibbs measure is an extreme invariant measure, it seems that (4.3.5) and (4.4.3) were essential for the proof in [2].

Remark: Let $m \in \mathcal{G}$. Let ρ be a $[0, +\infty)$ -valued bounded \mathcal{B} -measurable function. Suppose that $\int_{x \in X} \rho(x)m(dx) = 1$ holds. Then, $\rho m \in \mathcal{G}$ holds, if and only if $[\sigma_m\text{-a.s. } (x_0, x_1) : \rho(x_0) = \rho(x_1)]$ holds.

Proof: From Lemma 8, it is shown. (We do not go into details, as it is not difficult.) ■

Reference:

- [1] Fukushima, M., Oshima, Y., Takeda, M., *Dirichlet forms and symmetric Markov processes*, Walter de Gruyter & Co., Berlin, 1994.
- [2] Liggett, T. M., *Interacting particle systems*, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1985.